

SEARCH, FIND, CITE AND APPLY GRAMMAR RULES FOR TEXTGENERATION

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Abstract

To implement an open, transparent and reproducible research culture becomes more challenging with Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) [1]. Like all texts, texts produced by GenAI also have a syntactic and a semantic structure. This paper discusses on a conceptual level the application of grammars and grammar rules as citable units that can be used for transparent text generation for conferences and other application scenarios complementary to standard references, that are used e.g. in scientific publications.

INTRODUCTION

In scientific works citations and references are used as standard to refer to previous publications and to new scientific results on the existing scientific knowledge. Scientific publications are products and milestones of an evolutionary process and a joined collaborative effort of the scientific community. Publications in proceedings share common requirements for the possible scientific structure of papers. The syntax can be described with a specific grammar. Submissions of papers can be compliant with a specific grammar or may violate some of the rules. GenAI is more and more used and serves as an accelerator for text production.

In computer science a compiler converts a programme written in source programming language A into a functional equivalent code in a programming language B. During a compilation a tokenizer as the first phase is applied to convert the source code in language A as strings of symbols into an array of tokens. The list of tokens is transformed into an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) [2]. A parser reduces the string of the source code, which is written in language A, to a start symbol S. A specific set of rules of a specific grammar is implemented for this purpose. If that reduction was successful the source code in language A is regarded as syntactically correct. In this context a grammar (N, T, R, S) consists of a set of non-terminal symbols N , a set of terminal symbols T , a system of rules R and a start symbol S .

A generated AST represents the parsing process of the source code as semantic analysis. In the next step, the generated (and semantically attributed) AST is used to create an output source code in language B. The output language B can be binary/executable or a low-level programming language. So far the

1. parsing of source code in A and

2. generation in code B

can be distinguished conceptually.

In contrast to programming languages, in which the acceptance of source code in language A is boolean, we will apply fuzzy logic for describing the acceptance of natural language elements and their matching with grammar rules [3].

BASIC EXAMPLE

As a basic example the start symbol will be a general text represented as non-terminal symbol S. Rule (1)

$$S \rightarrow SCI|MA \quad (1)$$

includes an Open Resource (OR) expression, that allows to replace the non-terminal S either by SCI or by MA. The non-terminal symbol SCI represents a scientific article and MA is a manual e.g. for application of a workflow. This rule is branching into two different allowed text types.

$$SCI \rightarrow S_A S_I S_M S_R S_C \quad (2)$$

Rule (2) defines the grammar structure of a scientific paper. A scientific paper in this definition of the grammar consists of five sections represented by the non-terminal symbols S_A, S_I, S_M, S_R and S_C .

- S_A is the section *Abstract*,
- S_I the section *Introduction*,
- S_M the section *Methodology*,
- S_R the section *Results* and
- S_C represents the section *Conclusion*.

For a high-level programming language designed for computers a missing section or an extra section may lead to a violation of the grammar rules due to the defined set of rules. In natural language we can decompose a

- document SCI into sections, e.g. defined by rule (2),
- sections into paragraphs,
- paragraphs into sentences,
- sentences into words and other symbols classified by the lexical analysis into tokens like

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nouns, verbs, adjectives, mathematical and other symbols, etc.

The non-terminal symbol S_M for the section *Methodology* might be decomposed in other deterministic or optional substructures defined by the rules of the grammar.

CITATION OF GRAMMAR RULES

As mentioned in the introduction a text can be parsed and tested, if the structure of the document with the section follows a specific rule (e.g. is compliant with the specific rule). A compiler for a programming language needs deterministic true/false assessment for syntactical correctness. In a natural language processing we extend that concept to a probability distribution of OR-expressions in the rules $S \rightarrow SCI|MA$ e.g. stating, that start symbol S is generating a scientific article SCI with a probability of 0.7 and a manual MA with a probability of 0.3 as optional choices for the generation of text.

For citation or reference to a grammar rule $SCI \rightarrow S_A S_I S_M S_R S_C$ probability theory is not the appropriate approach, because in this context the matching is the gradual assignment of truth with a value between 0 and 1 (as full match). Fuzzy logic allows this gradual assignment of a matching result to a cited rule.

FUZZY LOGIC – MATCHING RULE

Fuzzy Logic extends the classical “true/false (1/0)” logic to a truth value of an expression (e.g. “the man is old”) with real number between 0 and 1 (according to Lofti Zadeh [4]). Fuzzy logic can be applied to grammar and languages [5]. Assuming we have a document with a parsed section structure $S_A S_I S_M S_R S_C$ then the document matches fully with the grammar rule mentioned in (2). In a parser a sequence $S_A S_I S_M S_R S_C$ of non-terminal symbols for the different sections can be reduced to the non-terminal symbol SCI . In natural language context a source text might not have all the sections and e.g. the section S_R is missing with $S_A S_I S_M S_C$ as section sequence. This leads to a fuzzy match with a value $4/5 = 80\%$ with the grammar rule mentioned in (2). Furthermore conceptionally a clear distinction between “cover” and “exceed” fuzzy values can be considered. Assuming the document inserts an additional section S_x at the end of the document, leading to a section structure $S_A S_I S_M S_R S_C S_x$, then the fuzzy “cover” is 1 (100%) but the “exceed” value is defined as $1/5$ (20%). Due to the fact that documents can have more than one extra section then the exceed fuzzy value can have the maximal value 1 for the exceed value.

The value 0 in “exceed” is a good match, because no extra terminal or non-terminal symbols exist in the text beyond the defined elements of the rule. If the section structure is exceeding more than 100% the given definition of the rule, the “exceed” value is cut to the maximum value of 1. This could be applied, because fuzzy values must be between 0 and 1. In the example rule above, the limitation to 1 would be applied if more

than five extra non-terminal symbols appear in the sequence of symbols that is compared with the definition of the rule. It is recommended to apply the fuzzy-NOT to the linguistic value [6] “exceed” to assign good matches to 1 and poor matches to 0. A value of 1 for “not-exceed” means that the document contains e.g. no extra sections (no exceeding terminal or non-terminal symbols) in comparison to the rule mentioned in (2). The fuzzification of the “cover” and “exceed” resp. “non-exceed” fuzzy values might be more complex than counting the symbols matching with definition or do not comply with definition of a specific rule.

The first conceptual approach is done for citations of grammar rules in text generation with gradual matching parameters for “exceed” and “cover” with application of fuzzy logic. In this context matching has to deal with vague information, that is also applied for Semantic Web languages [7]. We may address this issue by either extending current Semantic Web languages to cope with.

TEXT GENERATION – PROBABILITY

As mentioned above, text generation can be dependent of random experiments in an Abstract Syntax Tree, where the rule allows to have choices. A probability distribution on a finite set of options describes that mathematically. In this context text generation creates decision numbers that are used in the generative process when optional cases in a rule are possible. For the rule $S \rightarrow SCI|MA$ a random number r between 0 and 1 with a uniform distribution on the interval [0,1] determines the replacement for a start symbol S in the grammar. The non-terminal symbol SCI is selected if $r < 0.7$ and a non-terminal symbol for the manual MA is selected for replacement otherwise. For the selection process the interval [0,1] is decomposed in n subintervals for n different options in the grammar rule. To be transparent, in the derivation process from a tree node in AST to child nodes, these random numbers r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n for n different random experiments should be transparently assigned to the rules R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n of the grammar for which the random experiment is performed.

DOCUMENT OBJECT IDENTIFIER

A rule as part of a grammar is a digital object, that can be selected for application in text generation. Generalizing the approach described above conceptually, a digital object identifier (DOI) can be used to create a unique and persistent identifier for a rule and/or the corresponding subtree of an AST. Due to the fact that DOI can handle various other digital objects as well [8], the generation of multimedia documents, that include digital objects like audio, video, animation, data, charts, etc. a rule for text generation could be referred to in a consistent way. DOI is standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), so a reference for grammar rules follows an established work to provide unique identifiers. DOIs are an existing implementation of the Handle System. A DOI for a grammar rule provides the opportunity to fetch the rule and the corresponding subtree, because the DOI operates also consistently within

the Uniform Resource Identifiers (URI). The conceptual work of this paper allows generative models to be transparent, if they are applied not only on the root file of academic, professional, and government documents but also on the decomposition of the documents reflecting generative process in a transparent way.

LIMITATIONS OF THE CONCEPT

Context-free or context dependent grammars represent the syntactical structure of the document or a language [9]. This is similar to the validation and transparent tracing of document generation and DOI referencing of rules. Similar to the compilation of the source the semantic analysis might require a digital element with DOI reference to have e.g. the logic of an argumentation incorporated in the document generation. As an example we could conclude the statement C if the prerequisites

A_1, A_2, \dots, A_k represent a semantics. J_1, \dots, J_i are the justification for this conclusion C that are needed for the applicability of the conclusion. In general this is covered by the classical scientific citations, due to the fact that a statement in a scientific article should have references for justifications of the statement.

CONCLUSION

In this conceptual approach we consider a grammar rule as an identifiable digital object, that can be applied for text generation. Recursive application of rules towards a final generated text creates an Abstract Syntax Tree. The DOI serves as a mechanism to search, find and identify these grammar rules and ASTs in a unique way and supports the text generator with Uniform Resource Identifiers to fetch and apply the grammar rule for a specific generative task. For transparency the DOIs for the grammar rules could be inserted in the document similar to a citation to allow tracing of the generative process and distinguish the generated product from the manual add-ons of the author to the generated text. These manual add-ons to the text can be associated with intellectual contributions to the generated output.

Parts of the generative process are depending on random experiments in decision trees, for which a sequence of random numbers r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n determines the selection of options R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n for n different rules with decision options. Providing the sequence of random numbers r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n for the selection of options in rules R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n allows to reconstruct the process of text generation, because the previous randomized decision path is replaced by given static numbers, that are recorded during the randomized generation process. The application of rules does not

mean that an author who applied generative models needs to accept the result of a generative model completely. The editor may change the generated result and remove or add content elements in comparison to generated content referred to with DOIs. The matching process with a rule requires to represent a partial matching with a DOI referenced grammar rule or AST. Fuzzy values for "cover" and "exceed" can add transparency to the presented conceptual framework by measuring the similarity or compliance with a given DOI referenced rule or subtree.

Finally, by the application of the proposed concept a new scientific article would create not only the classical text content but also a syntax tree with its start grammar rule that other scientists can refer to, search for and apply on their text generation in other publications with a DOI based reference to syntactical structures.

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